

Duc, B., Lamamra, N. & Besozzi, R (2019). On-the-job trainers at the crossroad between training and production: How the labour market impacts their training activities. In F. Marhuenda & M.J. Chisvert-Tarazona (Eds.), *Pedagogical concerns and market demands in VET. Proceedings of the 3rd Crossing Boundaries in VET conference, Vocational Education and Training Network (VETNET)* (pp.308-312) <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2641079>

On-the-job trainers at the crossroad between training and production: How the labour market impacts their training activities

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Abstract

Dual vocational education and training (VET) is the most frequently chosen post-secondary track in Switzerland. Students who opt for this system alternate between periods of learning in vocational schools and periods of training in the workplace. The close relationship between the training system and the labour market is viewed positively when considering how it fosters occupational integration. However, both apprentices and on-the-job trainers are confronted with a major tension that exists in training companies between production and training. This paper focuses on this tension, to analyse the impact that the logics of the labour market have on workplace learning. Based on the results of a qualitative study focusing on on-the-job trainers, the contribution highlights this impact at three levels: how the logic of production interferes with the logic of training on a global level, how on-the-job trainers experience this tension in their daily work and how the demands associated to production influence the practices and content of the training.

Keywords

dual VET; on-the-job trainers; tension between production and training; semi-structured interviews

1 Introduction

Dual vocational education and training (VET) is the most frequently chosen post-secondary track in Switzerland (SEFRI, 2017). Students in this system alternate between periods of learning in vocational schools and periods of training in the workplace. This characteristic is viewed positively when considering how it supports smooth transitions from school to work (Cohen-Scali, 2000) and fosters occupational integration (SEFRI, 2017). However, given the close relationship that exists between the training system and the labour market (Hanhart, 2006), apprentices are often confronted almost immediately with working conditions and production needs (Masdonati, Lamamra, Gay-des-Combes, & De Puy, 2007). In this perspective, dual VET can be viewed as an instance of occupational socialisation (Dubar, 1996; Moreau, 2003), which is supported by on-the-job trainers who are active in training companies.

Considerable literature has been devoted to discussing the influence of the labour market on educational institutions (Felouzis, Maroy, & Van Zanten, 2013), but this paper aims to study training that is provided at the very heart of the world of work, within the training companies. This area can be considered as a laboratory that provides us with the opportunity

to conduct a precise analysis of the impact that the demands of the labour market place on education. Within this specific context, the impact can be found in a major tension that exists between two logics: producing and training (Moreau, 2003). Indeed, the transmission of knowledge and know-how with respect to an occupation is carried out most of the time in work situations, and it is not only “within” but also “by” and “for” productive activity (Thébault, 2018). At the same time, a specific pedagogy that is based on workplace learning can be identified (Billett, 2007; Filliettaz, Rémy, & Trebert, 2014; Fuller & Unwin, 2003).

This paper focuses on the tension that exists in training companies between production and training. Indeed, the current work considers training within a company as a prism through which to analyse the impact that the logics of the new labour market have on workplace learning. In so doing, the paper highlights the difficulties of training within a productive context.

Focusing on on-the-job trainers, this study aims to answer the following three research questions:

4. How does the logic of production interfere with the logic of training?
5. How do on-the-job trainers experience the tension between production and training?
6. How does this tension influence or constrain the training practices and training content to which on-the job trainers refer?

2 Methods

This contribution refers to a collective study and a PhD thesis focusing on on-the-job trainers and is based on a qualitative approach (interviews and observations) and a comprehensive perspective. Eighty semi-structured interviews have been conducted with people who train one or more apprentices in companies in French-speaking Switzerland. To echo the heterogeneity of this population, trainers were selected according to their genders, their years of experience, their statuses in the companies (employees, managers and employers) and their functions in relation to the training of apprentices (administrative responsibilities or human resources and daily training). These trainers work in companies of various sizes (micro, small and midsize businesses (SMB) and big companies) and from several sectors of activity, with or without a long tradition of training.

A thematic content analysis (Bardin, 1986) has been undertaken from deductive and inductive perspectives to identify the central elements relating to the experience of a population that has rarely been studied. For the purpose of this paper, the analysis focuses on the following elements: the conditions under which the training activity is carried out as well as the constraints encountered and the practices and content of training to which on-the-job trainers refer. This contribution is also based on a typological approach (Schnapper, 2012). A typology of on-the-job trainers, which is specific to the PhD thesis, has been constructed with the help of two analytical axes: relationship and commitment to work (strong commitment to work and identification with the occupation or postures of withdrawal and distance from work or occupation) and the apprentices’ perceptions, which have led to the emergence of different conceptions among the apprentices (figures of student or workers).

3 Results

According to the research questions, the influence of the labour market on training in a company will be discussed at three levels.

First, on a global level, it appears that the logic of production (rhythms of production, economic pressures, etc.) tends to take precedence over other areas in training companies. Sometimes training seems to take on a secondary role and be optional, as the apprentices are expected to be productive at very early stages of their apprenticeships. This is particularly true in the context of SMBs, which are subjected to important economic pressures and strong competition. Surprisingly, the same logics are found in the training centres of big companies that were initially fully dedicated to training. Indeed, these centres, which could temporarily provide protected environments for training, are becoming new production spaces. This first level of research shows the degree to which the demands of production interfere with training logics, which has consequences on the daily work of on-the-job trainers and also on the training practices and content.

Indeed, at the level of the daily work of on-the-job trainers, the analysis points out that they experience the tension between production and training more than any others who are involved in VET. This tension sometimes seems to be a double bind. Their objective is twofold: the success of their apprentices and the achievement of their production objectives. At the same time, most of the trainers do not have specific times during which they can train apprentices; they have neither specification documents nor any discharge to fulfil their training functions (Besozzi, Perrenoud, & Lamamra, 2017). As a result, on-the-job trainers lack adequate time to train their apprentices, and this is a pervasive theme in their discourse. Moreover, the rhythms of production and the requirements associated with some occupations, such as interruptions by customers, fragment the time that could be dedicated to formative activities. As a consequence, trainers have to find strategies so that they can continue to train, such as doing the training when there are the gaps in their work, during their breaks or outside of working hours or by encouraging self-training among their apprentices (Baumeler & Lamamra, 2018). These strategies allow them to carry on training without having any real time in which to do it and to deal with what can sometimes appear as a contradiction. Although several such strategies are experienced in companies of different sizes, this is particularly the case in micro firms (Baumeler & Lamamra, 2018).

The dominance of the production logics also has an influence on the level of the training practices themselves (pedagogy, assignment of tasks and guidance). The fragmented periods of time that trainers have make it difficult for them to set up specific pedagogies to guide their apprentices in learning the occupations. In some situations, the training context forces trainers to renounce any pedagogy, at least temporarily, and to confine apprentices to less formative tasks. Learning at the workplace, then, appears more and more like a way to present apprentices directly with work and the demands of the labour market for effectiveness and productivity, inviting them to become productive and autonomous very quickly. However, these confrontations do vary according to the perceptions that on-the-job trainers have of their apprentices and can range from direct involvement in work and productivity, where the apprentices are considered as workers, to more progressive involvement combined with guidance that evolves over time, where the apprentices are seen as pupils. In addition, depending on the profiles they have of their apprentices as future workers (executives or executants), the expectations vary from autonomy and self-responsibility on the one hand to the execution of only simple and repetitive tasks on the other. The content of the training is also influenced by the labour market. This can be illustrated by the references to transversal skills that on-the-job trainers make in their discourse about what is central to transmit to apprentices (Duc, Perrenoud, & Lamamra, 2018), reflecting the constant use of such strategies in the world of work.

4 Conclusion

In conclusion, the entire training experience in a company, as it is perceived by on-the-job trainers, is influenced by the world of work and its dominant logics. The initial elements seem to confirm that with respect to the tension between production and training that is highlighted by Moreau (2003) production has clearly become dominant over training. As a result, training in the workplace is greatly influenced by productivity constraints and requirements. For training to take place, on-the-job trainers must play central roles in the mediation work between these two logics (adjusting training conditions, choosing different modalities and contents, etc.) (Thébault, 2018). The trainers do use strategies to cope with this situation, both in practice, such as training during gap times and giving extra time for training, and in their discourse, through highlighting the training components of their work and placing value on models of progressive pedagogy and a certain representation of apprentices. All of this illustrates that in dual VET on-the-job trainers want to go on with their training; in spite of the constraints they experience, this aspect of their work gives meaning to their professional activities.

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